

ECONOMIC VALORISATION OF PERSONAL DATA AND LEGAL BASES: FOR A “*DIGITAL PRIVACY NEW DEAL*”

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Abstract

This article considers the possibility of an economic valorisation of personal data without the consent of data subjects but rather, alternative legal bases such as article 6(1)(b) of the GDPR (performance of a contract), or article 6(1)(f) GDPR (legitimate interest of the controller). For article 6(1)(b), the concept of *exchange-commerce* and *RTM* is contemplated, where consideration is paid by the data subject, allowing (like a license) the temporary use of some personal data for profiling and/or marketing purposes by the controller. While several remuneration models can exist, the main focus of jurists should be on making these models safe and balanced for data subjects, rather than prohibiting them. Moreover, when considering the legitimate interest of the controller, rather than it being recognized only as a 'quasi' right if harmless and indifferent to the rights of data subjects, this legal base can implement the "bridge of crossing and balancing" between privacy and fundamental rights and freedoms. Consequently, instead of anchoring to the idealization of consent as the only legal basis suitable for legitimizing the commercial exploitation of personal data, the focus should be on the accountability of the controllers of the processing as well as safeguarding data-driven fundamental rights and freedoms, without suffocating, but indeed encouraging economic initiative and innovation.

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A very delicate issue is on the agenda of the Authorities as well as of the boards of large and small companies, and which above all, is crucial for the pandigital and metaversal future that awaits us: Is it possible to conceive an economic valorisation of personal data - for example through behavioural profiling or personalized marketing - without the consent of the data subject? Or, even, without basing the processing on any of the legal bases indicated in Article 6 of the GDPR²? A mere regulatory and interpretative tug of war is not at stake: there is a world view, a Weltanschauung, and the correct balance between rights, freedom, interests in our lives of tomorrow. And allow me to state a point of self-criticism: I have the feeling that many of us privacy experts - in institutions and in the private sector - often tend to radicalize and mono-focus the weights of protections in the subjects that belong to us, operating perfectly rational syllogisms, in the abstract, but, to the test of the facts, are disproportionate and disconnected from the current reality. Sometimes the specialist misses the big picture.

1. INTRODUCTION: SIX FIXED POINTS TO AVOID MISUNDERSTANDING

Let us immediately clarify some points and fix some poles to orient ourselves and dispel slippery ambiguities.

First: the formula "without the consent of the data subject" can and will never mean "against the will of the data subject".

Second: as rightly pointed out by the Italian Data Protection Authority (Garante per la protezione dei dati personali), in the Decision of 7 July, 2022 addressed to Tik Tok³, if information is stored or read on the user's / subscriber's terminal, the special E-privacy discipline - deriving from art. 5.3 of Directive 2002/58 / EC and, in Italy, by art. 122 of the Privacy Code⁴ - will inevitably apply. However, that discipline applies to the data collection phase (for which a request for an *ad hoc* consent is mandatory, without preventing *any technical storage or access for the sole purpose of carrying out the transmission of a communication over an electronic communications network, or as strictly necessary in order for the provider of an information society service explicitly requested by the subscriber or user to provide the service*) and not to the subsequent processing of the data now "freed" by the first consent. If you have any doubts, you can read - among others - the Guidelines 01/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications⁵.

Third: the right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right. It must be reconciled with other fundamental rights and freedoms, both of individuals and of other legal

² Regulation UE no. 2016/679

³ [TikTok: Italian SA warns against 'personalised' ads based on legitimate interest | European Data Protection Board \(europa.eu\)](https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/edpb_guidelines_202001_connected_vehicles_v2.0_adopted_en.pdf)

⁴ Italian Legislative Decree no. 196/2003

⁵ Guidelines 01/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/edpb_guidelines_202001_connected_vehicles_v2.0_adopted_en.pdf

entities, as recognized by the Constitutions and, if we wish to remain Eurocentric, by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Simply reading Recital 4 of the GDPR provides unequivocal confirmation: *"The processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind. The right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights, in accordance with the principle of proportionality. This Regulation respects all fundamental rights and observes the freedoms and principles recognized in the Charter as enshrined in the Treaties, in particular the respect for private and family life, home and communications, the protection of personal data, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression and information, freedom to conduct a business, the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial, and cultural, religious and linguistic diversity."*

If we combine it with article 52 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, in the matter of the principle of proportionality to which legislators and institutions (and therefore also the Authorities) are bound in the first place, the picture is completed: *"Any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognized by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognized by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others"*. It should be noted that this applies both to the protection of privacy and personal data, and vice versa, to safeguard the rights and freedoms of others, which cannot be suffocated by privacy and protection of personal data when interpreted and applied in a tyrannical and maximalist way.

Fourth: no one, least of all myself, could ever want a world in which human beings - and their fundamental and inviolable rights, including, but not limited to privacy - are debased by controllers and transformed into mere means to pursue technological and business ends.

Fifth: the consent of the data subject (legal basis provided for in Articles 6.1.a), 7 and 9.2.a) GDPR) is a valuable legal institution but not a *passe-partout*; it does not always and invariably constitute the key to truly protect data subjects - who may lack the time, will, strength, competence, prudence, and many other small or great talents, to understand what they are saying "yes" to with a trivial flag - nor is it always useful to correctly balance the right to data protection with other rights, freedoms, interests in the "all digital" era (think of the usability of services by users / subscribers, free economic initiative, innovative research and development, etc.).⁶

Sixth: regardless of the issues relating to the legal bases, personal data must always be processed in compliance with the general principles of law (including those provided for in Article 5 of the GDPR).

2. WHAT MODELS OF VALORISATION OF PERSONAL DATA? THE LEGAL BASES OF THE GDPR, BEYOND CONSENT

So, let us take the six points listed above as acceptable and firm. Let us now ask ourselves whether it is possible, in principle and subject to further special regulations applicable on a case-by-case basis, to hypothesize an economic exploitation of personal data - for example,

⁶ [Commodification of Data is the Problem, Not the Solution - Why Placing a Price Tag on Personal Information May Harm Rather Than Protect Consumer Privacy - Future of Privacy Forum \(fpf.org\)](#) – Paragraph "Why Should We Be Skeptical of Consent as a Solution for Consumer Privacy?"

the processing of data for purposes of online commercial profiling or direct marketing with non-automated means - without the consent of the data subject.⁷

Without consent, the residual cases that can be hypothesized - moving within the margins set by the legal bases of the GDPR - are basically two, namely that the economic valorisation of the data takes place: 1. on a legal basis of necessity for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract; (art. 6 par. 1.b) GDPR) or 2. for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child (Article 6 paragraph 1 letter f) GDPR). Apparently, *tertium non datur*, which in this context - data-driven - seems to be a Latin expression with a happy, appropriate, double meaning.

Let us start with the first hypothesis, relating to the possibility that the processing of personal data is "necessary for the execution of a contract of which the data subject is a part or for the execution of pre-contractual measures adopted at the request of the same". It contains, in truth, two possible distinct declensions; the more advanced one comes to contemplate a possible synallagmatic exchange between performance (service rendered by the supplier / controller) and consideration (economic enhancement of the license to use one's data for a purpose provided by the data subject). The other more classic and "orthodox" declination refers only to the processing of data strictly indispensable and instrumental with respect to the service provided by the controller, without being a substantial part of a counter-performance of the data subject but, solely, an essential instrumental component of the service due by the controller.

3. THE LICENSE TO USE YOUR DATA AS CONTRACTUAL COUNTER-PERFORMANCE OF THE SUBJECT DATA: THE *EXCHANGE-COMMERCE*⁸

I have been writing and presenting legal essays on these aspects for more than ten years (theorising a form of negotiation that I have called "*exchange-commerce*") and, in 2018, I touched on these issues with Isabella de Michelis of Slonghella in the paper "An Introduction to the Right to Monetize Data (RTM)⁹".

In *exchange-commerce* and RTM, do you want to monetize and make the right to the protection of personal data marketable (and renounceable!)? No. Privacy rights are fundamental, inviolable, unavailable: any renunciation of them by the data subjects would be void, in exchange for money or nothing. For this reason too, businesses are a little perplexed, because business is based on the monetization of the exercise of privacy rights in the name and on behalf of others: how can one, for profit, commercially abuse the exercise of a fundamental and inviolable right, which, allegedly, would like to help exercise and protect? If the data are personal, they will never be expropriated by controllers from the data subject, who will not be able to do without the related rights, even voluntarily.

When we talk about *exchange-commerce* and RTM, the discourse is quite different and concerns the possibility of providing a consideration paid by the data subject in the essential object of the contract allowing (like a license) the temporary use of some personal data for profiling and / or marketing purposes by third party controllers of the processing. This license

⁷ [Data Protection and Data Commerce: Friends or Foes? \(degruyter.com\)](https://degruyter.com)

⁸ Landi, A., L'exchange commerce. La Direttiva (UE) 2019/770, in the volume "Privacy e libero mercato digitale", editor Luca Bolognini, Giuffrè Francis Lefebvre, 2021

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/58619396/An_Introduction_to_the_Right_to_Monetize_Data_RTM

would have a recognized economic value, corresponding to a consideration in terms of goods or services by the controllers of the processing. Although I use the conditional tense, this already represents the business model of many digital operators today. Nobody would touch the fundamental and inviolable rights, which are always, and in any case, exercisable by the data subject and never subject to assignment or license. And here, in the range of usability of personal data for commercial purposes, that value could constitute an alternative "medium of exchange in kind" to money in order to use digital services. It is important to note and underline that: the value of the obligation to let the data be used for certain purposes and in certain contexts would be considered as relevant, and not the value of the data itself. There would be no transfer of ownership of the data (no data commoditization¹⁰, in short) or worse, of the rights, in the *exchange-commerce*.

In the *exchange-commerce* and enhancement (use) of personal data scheme which I have just described, one could choose between different remuneration models: the license value could be calculated according to market logic, without aggravating it from the surplus value that can be generated by the controller of the processing in the transformation and "processing" of that same data (after all, the investments and processing techniques are the know-how of the processing controller, who may be more or less good at exploiting that information); or, scenarios could be imagined in which the data subject is recognized as having a sort of right of economic use of personal data, as a percentage, as happens in copyright cases with actors, models, performers, artists and so on. What matters is that there is no one and only possible and desirable remuneration model: some operators will offer a good service, simply without asking users / subscribers / data subjects to pay money in exchange for the provisional license to exploit some data; others will additionally recognize prizes or percentages. It will depend on market contexts and business options.

The processing of personal data, however, does not have the same value for everyone and in every case; this is why it seems almost impossible to conceive the possibility of class action privacy, strictly understood, due to the non-homogeneity of the values involved, and the fact that privacy rights (and their violations) are very personal and not estimated by general categories¹¹.

The focus of the confrontation between jurists should not be on the general unlawfulness and fundamentalist prohibition of *exchange-commerce* and RTM scenarios but, vice versa, on the identification of the conditions that could make those scenarios safe, correct and balanced for data subjects. Similar to what already happens for the protection of consumers and competition, conditions such as the following should be noted: the possible discrimination between data subjects (to avoid privacy becoming a luxury only for those who can pay in money, certain processing of certain data in certain areas of public, collective or general interest - that is, not in any area, in my opinion - should not be allowed, where free and privacy-proof alternatives for equivalent services are not available), the imbalance in the synallagm (sensitive data or too much data in exchange for services of little value), the imbalance and unsuitability of the parties involved (vulnerable and weak subjects, lack of transparency, unfair bidding and contractualization practices), the imbalance in the effects of a withdrawal or a contractual resolution based on exercise - always possible - of privacy rights, which would break the scheme of "*data ut des*", the competitive imbalance due to capitalization asymmetric information, and other criteria, relative and not absolute. The

¹⁰ [Commoditization of Data is the Problem, Not the Solution - Why Placing a Price Tag on Personal Information May Harm Rather Than Protect Consumer Privacy - Future of Privacy Forum \(fpf.org\)](#)

¹¹ I supported this impossibility in the essay, written with Marco Emanuele Carpenelli, "The representation of rights in the field of personal data protection, between multi-subjective actions and class actions" in the Italian book "Azione di classe: la riforma italiana e le prospettive europee" (Giappichelli, 2020)

Digital Services Act, the Digital Markets Act and the Data Act are moving precisely in this direction, at least in principle, despite numerous critical issues.

4. THE CLASSIC CONTRACTUAL EXECUTION

Then there is the more classic and less "pushed" sub-hypothesis of the *exchange-commerce* model, which must be taken into consideration for the legal basis pursuant to art. 6.1.b) GDPR: that is, although not economically valued as a counter-performance of the data subject, the processing of data is, in any case, considered indispensable for the execution of the contract of which the data subject is a party, or to carry out pre-contractual agreements adopted at the request of the same. In this scenario, the processing of personal data is not in itself the subject of the license (i.e., the consideration of the data subject), but remains entirely on the part of the controller, i.e., it constitutes an essential instrumental component of the contracted service that the controller must return to the data subject. The complaint made on several occasions, also by the European data protection authorities in such cases, is that the processing of data is not strictly and essentially necessary for the contracted service. Here, at times, the reasoning seems to lead to questionable and not very modern conclusions. We use an easy-to-grasp metaphor that can help understand the matter. Imagine the request, contracted by a data subject-passenger with a transport company, to be transferred from Milan to Vienna; a restrictive or unbalanced interpretation in favour of environmental rights would lead to the consideration that in absence of a clear specification in the transport contract on the type of vehicle to be used, or to ensure (extreme) compliance with the principles of environmental protection, that trip must be understood on board a horse, or a pedal vehicle. And not in a car, train, or plane. Would this approach be reasonable and proportionate in the twenties of the 21st century? Would it consider the living and material variation of constitutional principles, as well as the customs linked to the times, the state of the art and the technology? Unless you want to prohibit planes, trains and cars in the name of a misunderstood respect for other rights, freedoms and interests, or an equally equivocal and fundamentalist interpretation of the general principles of law, the answer could only be: no; a *by default* transportation on horseback or by bicycle from Milan to Vienna (but also over shorter distances) would be unreasonable and anachronistic.

5. LEGITIMATE INTEREST AS A BASIS FOR THE ECONOMIC VALORISATION OF PERSONAL DATA

Let us now briefly deal with the hypothesis of legitimate interest as a possible legal basis for the secondary enhancement of data. Art. 6 par. 1 letter f) GDPR allows the processing of personal data when "necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child".

The definition of legitimate interest can be of two distinct types. A first option is to consider the "legitimate interest" not as subjective rights or fundamental freedoms of the controller or third parties, but forms of "weakened rights and freedoms" or "quasi-rights / quasi-liberties", however mildly deserving of protection in the legal system: this option borrows defining fragments from the institution of the "legitimate interest", typical of Italian administrative law. It is clear that, due to its intrinsic weakness understood in this way, the "legitimate interest" could hardly hold up in the face of the weight of fundamental rights and freedoms of a data

subject, whose data are at stake: the legitimate interest as "quasi- right / quasi-freedom "can be recognized and "breathe" only if totally harmless and indifferent to the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

In this sense, I refer to the 2020 decision of the Dutch Data Protection Authority in the VoetbalTV case, in which the Supervisor declared that the legitimate interest of the data controller could not be recognized as a valid legal basis for the processing of personal data, in the case of purely commercial business purposes; that decision was then overturned by the court¹² before which it had been challenged, denying the Dutch Authority's thesis on the impossibility of recognizing a legitimate interest as a valid legal basis for the processing of data for purely commercial purposes. Finally, in the month of July 2022, the Council of State of the Netherlands intervened¹³, which unfortunately did not definitively resolve the issue on the merits, but limited itself to confirming the appeal sentence and finding regarding the secondary use of personal data operated by VoetbalTV, including interests that are not purely commercial. The diatribe remains open.

Thinking that a legitimate interest of a controller or third parties can support the processing of personal data only if not purely commercial would be tantamount to considering the economic activity as not deserving of legal protection, and in any case not "worthy" of a real balancing. This orientation, in the opinion of the writer and to paraphrase Fouché, would be worse than a crime, it would be an error. That a purely commercial purpose should be considered as *a priori* unsuitable to meet the requirements of legitimate interest, without even passing through the three-part test¹⁴ and case-by-case evaluation, is not reasonable, and risks betraying the spirit of the GDPR itself. Not surprisingly, in Regulation 679/2016, in addition to the now famous Recital 4, we find expressly and unconditionally engraved in Recital 47 that "the processing of personal data for direct marketing purposes may be regarded as carried out for a legitimate interest". The *ratio legis* cannot be more explicit than that. These are *de jure condendo* considerations, and it is true that the e-privacy discipline still requires user's/subscriber's consent for direct marketing with automated tools, except for that typified case of substantial "legitimate interest *ex lege*", the *soft-spam* e-mail.

6. BETWEEN “STRONG” LEGITIMATE INTEREST AND EXTRA-PRIVACY LEGITIMATION

It is necessary to broaden thought and vision. The GDPR does not in itself exhaust the entirety of the legal protections in relations between human beings. Precisely for this reason, the second defining option of "legitimate interest" can be disconnected from that of "quasi-right / quasi-freedom", considered to be fragile, rigid, and unable to support the processing of personal data except in very rare and fortunate cases. The "legitimate interest" envisaged in the GDPR could, on the other hand, be intended in a strong and resilient way, as an institution with weight and meaning: an **"implementing bridge of crossing and balancing"** between privacy and other fundamental rights and freedoms referred to in Recital 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation.

There are two cases, in fact: either we conceive that - alongside the universe of personal data protection - there are other universes, with planets and stars (fundamental rights and freedoms of different nature, for example freedom of expression or information, freedom of

¹² Dutch Court Annuls Gdpr Fine Imposed On Streaming Platform VoetbalTV For Distributing Sports Content To Large Audiences - [Article \(coe.int\)](#)

¹³ [Dutch Court closes VoetbalTV case, but balance to the GDPR Legitimate Interest is yet to be restored - FEDMA](#)

¹⁴ [What is the 'legitimate interests' basis? | ICO](#)

business, etc.) to legitimize non-GDPR processing of personal data and regardless of the legal bases listed therein; or we admit that the only way to bring those planets and stars from other universes back into the privacy universe is, in fact, the bridge of "legitimate interest". If so, this legal basis, depending on the case, can assume an important dimension and a significant systematic role, capable of supporting the processing of personal data with strength and elasticity. As for the fact that the business activity is not exercised in many situations by natural persons, this does not detract from the legitimacy and merit of the balance between different rights and fundamental freedoms, and their traceability to legal persons: that the rights and fundamental freedoms must also be recognized in social formations and therefore in legal entities other than natural persons is, frankly, difficult to contest in the Third Millennium.

7. A PRIVACY “NEW DEAL” BETWEEN FREEDOM, RISK MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY

The choice of a method of providing a (contracted) service and of the secondary elements surrounding it (which we could lead back to "legitimate interests", better understood in a strong sense as "crossing bridges and balancing" between privacy and other rights / freedoms fundamental) in the private sphere, does not correspond to a casual and hungry whim - and to think it would be a prejudice; this free choice of business is not comparable or superimposable to the rigidity of the provision of administrative powers, procedures and margins for action for a PA. A law, regulation, or an inflexible and specious contractual agreement should not be necessary to legitimize a private business model, but rather the fair match between the wishes and reasonable expectations - explicit or implicit - of the parties involved should count. For example, except to the extent that it is expressly prohibited by law and / or is objectively harmful (but the risk and quantum should be assessed in order to balance), no regulatory authority - ex ante or ex post - should be able to prevent or contest recipes, menus, ways of cooking and serving food to its customers in a restaurant. Nor could it be possible to review and impose the methods of customer relations (CRM) by the service personnel.

In any case, even when evaluating the non-contractual profiles, the state of the art and technique, the material Constitution and customs should be taken into account. This reasoning - which I have intentionally simplified with catering - is valid, a fortiori, in the digital environment: what sense would it have to impose paper and analogue dimensions in contexts that are now natively digital? Being able to implement a service delivery model, rather than another, corresponds to a mechanism of economic enhancement of tangible and intangible assets - therefore, also of personal and non-personal data - which belongs to the margins of business freedom, freedom of expression, of the right to information, and the list could grow. Otherwise, all economic activities that provide the same services could not differentiate themselves in a competitive way, and should comply, as public bodies, with the procedural requirements of the statutory provisions. Unreal, direct, harmful precisely to the freedoms and fundamental rights of all, first data subjects, consumers, citizens, users and subscribers.

It is natural and obvious that greater freedom must be matched proportionately with greater attention to risks and greater responsibilities on the part of those who carry out digital business activities. No one would ever wish for the absence of safeguards and remedies for people and their information. But rather than anchoring to the idealization of consent as the only legal basis suitable for legitimizing the commercial exploitation of personal data (it is not in fact in many situations), and trying to impose business models as provided above -

by syndicating in an imperative key, the goodness of one or the badness of the other - which are not limited to the cases provided for by law or overtly, not only abstractly, remotely and potentially harmful to the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects, it would make sense to focus on the accountability of the controllers of the processing and address the dynamics of protection of personal data in the digital context, according to an Aquilian criterion, on the one hand, and tolerating the inevitable contractual and regulatory atypicality, on the other. This would also mean offering users/contractors/data subjects new and powerful features that are more transparent, personalized and targeted to exercise their rights in a digital environment, exploiting the same profiling technologies normally used for commercial purposes¹⁵.

As clearly illustrated by Giovanni De Gregorio and Pietro Dunn in their paper¹⁶ awarded by the My Data is Mine 2021 initiative¹⁷, it would be possible to promote the methodological approach to a new digital constitutionalism, balancing rights, freedoms and competing interests through the balancing filter of risk assessment and management. It seems useless and harmful to insist on the enforcement of a legal basis such as prior consent, since the totalizing and native metaversal immersion¹⁸ of human, entrepreneurial, institutional, social, consumerist, civic, professional, academic, creative, et al relationships and interactions. .. will gradually make the consent, more often than not, cumbersome, tiring, fictitious or, worse, confusing tool, thus counterproductive for the protections of the data subjects themselves. Overcoming the impasse of the legal basis - linked to a well-intentioned but too rigid application of the principle of lawfulness, admitting the freedom of business models, or accepting the legitimate interest as a "crossing and balancing bridge" in the economic valorisation of personal data - except in particular and sensitive cases or cases of too high risk would imply an increase in the levels of transparency, fairness, accountability and trust. A **Privacy "New Deal"** for the protection and enhancement of personal data in the "all digital", which will ensure the highest possible degree - never absolutizing, always relativized and balanced - of safeguarding data-driven fundamental rights and freedoms, without suffocating, but indeed encouraging economic initiative and innovation.

¹⁵ Bolognini L., Carpenelli M.E., PRIVACY NUTRITION LABELS VS. PRIVACY DYNAMIC TARGETING - Ex-ante and ex-post models for the administration of privacy information and the exercise of data subject rights
https://www.academia.edu/49071736/PRIVACY_NUTRITION_LABELS_VS_PRIVACY_DYNAMIC_TARGETING_Ex_ante_and_ex_post_models_for_the_administration_of_privacy_information_and_the_exercise_of_data_subject_rights

¹⁶ De Gregorio G., Dunn P., [My Data is Mine](https://www.academia.edu/49071736/My_Data_is_Mine) - Profiling under Risk-based Regulation: Bringing together the GDPR and the DSA
https://assets.ctfassets.net/iapmw8ie3ije/5EuxLPaUIsgGt7R6PgeuFK/c9269e55e10bb2a7a0b392624c08f4d0/De_Gregorio_Dunn_My_Data_is_Mine_1.pdf

¹⁷ [2021 My Data is Mine Award to Giovanni De Gregorio and Pietro Dunn - MediaLaws](https://www.academia.edu/49071736/2021_My_Data_is_Mine_Award_to_Giovanni_De_Gregorio_and_Pietro_Dunn_-_MediaLaws)

¹⁸ Bolognini L., Carpenelli M.E., The future of personal data in the Metaverse
https://www.academia.edu/75598264/The_future_of_personal_data_in_the_Metaverse